

RHETORIC IN THE ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract: In this article, the supply of the cardiovascular system through a closed system, hemodynamic parameters and biomechanics of blood flow were studied in academic lyceum students. The obtained results from a mathematical model allow to evaluate the cardiovascular system.

Keywords: Systolic pressure, diastolic pressure, average blood pressure, heart beat volume, blood volume from the left ventricle, blood density, blood velocity in the aorta, heart work, heartbeat cycle, heart rate, minute volume of blood.

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Scientific research directed at studying rhetoric aspect of speech culture is being carried out in a number of prestigious leading scientific centers and higher educational institutions of the world. N.A. Kashey, G.M. Yarmarkina, Z.I. Kurtseva and other scholars approached to rhetoric aspect from Russian point of view.⁴⁰ Scholars such as V.O. Nemchenko approached to this topic from teaching point of view.⁴¹

In both languages women achieve a speech efficiency by pleasing, asking politely (*Please, Geordie, just for me, Geordie / Ҳамида бону ёшли кўзларини Ҳумоюнга тикди. Йиғлаб илтижо қилди: «Бу қандай кўргулик?»*). They use repetition, exclamatory sentences in their speech (*will you enter... will you be there... Geordie... please, Geordie / ...муслмонлар! Бу қандай кўргулик? Мен боламни хавф-хатарга қандай таилаб кетгаймен, муслмонлар!; Will you be there, Geordie? / Наҳотки Ҳиндистонни бутунлай тарк этсак? Please, Geordie! / Илтимос, асалим!*). Expressiveness is gradually increased in their speech (*You must win. You must beat that Weber. I shall wish it with all my heart! I want you to win, Geordie / ...менинг дилимда қанча орзулар бор эди... Зора ўғлимиз ҳам шу мамлакатга чин фарзандлик хизматини қилса. Наҳотки бу орзулар бари пуч чиқса!*).

Women of the both nations try to express their speech politely and softly, this way expressiveness in their speech is increased. In persuading they use terms of endearment, praising words (*laddie – йигитча, darling – азизам, you are very*

⁴⁰ www.rhetor.ru/

⁴¹ Немченко В.А. Формирование внутреннего убеждения судьи в административном процессе Украины: Автореф. дис. ...канд. Юрид. науч. – Запорожье, ЗНУ, 2013. – 20 с.;

beautiful tonight – сиз бугун жуда ҳам гўзалсиз каби). While using terms of endearment English women in major cases use noun phrases, Uzbek women use verbal phrases additional to noun phrases (such as *my love, sweet, honey* / *жоним, айланай, ўргилай*).

They often use paralinguistic means such as crying, pleasing («*Have a mercy on me*», *she said cring* / *Ҳамида бону ёшли кўзларини Ҳумоюнга тикди. Йиғлаб илтижо қилди...*).

They also achieve a speech efficiency by giving advice (*You must be very gentle, David. Now you must try to bring each other happiness. Marriage is full of difficulties, David* / *Болам, укаларингга доим ибрат бўлгин, сен каттасан, уларни доимо тўғри йўлга бошлагин, жон болам. Мен энди кексайиб қолдим...*). This linguistic phenomenon is mostly used in Uzbek women's speech. They make very long sentences while giving advice and express their speech in whole texts. They remind the patterns taken from narrated stories and the religious book Hadis (such as *Ҳадисда шундай дейилган..., Қуронда бундай деб ёзилган...*). Meanwhile the English women make shorter sentences, they just speak to the point.

In dialogic rhetoric praying for the sake of a listener is mostly used by Uzbek women (such as *Худо хайрларингизни берсин, умринг узоқ бўлгур, барака топ*). This linguistic phenomenon is mostly used in older women's speech. English women rarely use these kind of phrases (such as *God bless you*).

English women try to make an impact on men by being angry and irritable.⁴²They can use *Black English* and foul language (*Hell with it. The hell with them*). Meanwhile Uzbek women mostly use cursing in their speech (*Қирон келсин илоё, ўша немисларга! Тур ўрнингдан-е. Э, башаранг қурсин*).

Moreover, the Uzbek women make their speech more efficient by using phrases such as “*одамлар, қўшнилар нима дейди?*” (What do other people, neighbours say about it?). This linguistic phenomenon is not used by English women, in these cases they can use the phrase *shame on you*.

English men widely use pleasing sentences while talking to women. Uzbek men prefer to be a bit proud in this situation and they don't use linguistic units that have a pleasing meaning.

In both languages religious words and phrases, wishing good wishes, praying for the sake of a listener, advising are used (*God bless you..., be healthy.../ умрингдан барака топ..., Аллоҳим ўз паноҳида асрасин..., доимо иноқ бўлинглар, бир-бирингизни қўллаб-қувватланглар...*). But this linguistic phenomenon is mainly used in Uzbek men's speech.

So, according to above mentioned facts and examples, we may conclude that different aspects of lifestyle, culture, religion and other factors that are associated

⁴²Георгия Н.Ю. Просодия убеждения в английской диалогической речи: Автореф. дис. ...канд. филол. науч. – Одесса: ОНУ, 2005. – 21 с.

with these both nations really reflect the existance of national gender peculiarities in speech culture.

MANBALAR:

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3. www.rhetor.ru/ and others.